

STUDY PROTOCOL

Methods for living evidence synthesis: a systematic review protocol [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

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Abstract

Background: Living evidence (LE) refers to the methodological process that permits new research findings to be continually incorporated to evidence synthesis as they become available. This approach is of great value in the resolution of relevant and rapidly changing clinical questions. To date, the methods to carry out this type of synthesis are not completely defined, and great variability is observed in the approaches used by different groups of authors.

Objective: To identify and summarise the current methods used for living evidence synthesis.

Methods: We will conduct a systematic literature review of systematic reviews, overviews, and network meta-analyses that have used "living evidence synthesis" as part of their methods. The search will be conducted in Medline (via PubMed) and the Epistemonikos database. Two reviewers will independently screen each article for eligibility, extract data, and assess the methodological quality standards of the study accordingly. This protocol is being registered in Prospero.

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2
version 2 (revision) 21 Mar 2022		 view
version 1 28 Sep 2021	 view	 view

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Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Keywords

Systematic review, Living Systematic Review, Evidence-based medicine, Evidence Synthesis, Living Evidence Synthesis, Living network metanalysis

This article is included in the [Healthcare and Policy](#) collection.

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Plain language summary

“Living Evidence” refers to a new method for developing synthesis of research evidence, that allows to maintain the information up to date, as new evidence is constantly incorporating as soon as it appears. The basis for the “Living Evidence” has been established, however, the way it is carried out and the methods used by investigators are still unknown.

The objective of this review is to assess and summarise the methods and procedures used by authors to keep the evidence “living”.

In order to meet our objective, we will search for all types of articles reporting “Living Evidence” synthesis to answer a health question. We will search for them in different databases and select the studies that meet the characteristics for “Living Evidence” established in advance. We will extract the information related to the methods used by authors to constantly identify new evidence, and determine how to incorporate the new findings in previous evidence synthesis. This information will be analysed and presented in a descriptive way.

Introduction

The exponential proliferation of scientific studies and their dispersion through a multitude of scientific journals poses a significant challenge to professionals, given their limited time to keep permanently updated in their respective disciplines. Therefore, systematic reviews (SR) and other derived evidence synthesis products (e.g., clinical practice guidelines [CPG]) are valuable informational tools that try to bring scientific evidence closer to the end user, facilitating its interpretation and application¹. However, SRs often do not have the expected impact²⁻⁵. Among various reasons that could be mentioned, the rapid outdated of their conclusions⁶ is the one that most limits its use and potential impact, making the enormous efforts of developing them largely sterile.

There are areas of high scientific productivity, due to the public health importance of the condition, or the high level of development and technological innovation dedicated to it. It is in these areas where using outdated information poses a major challenge to clinical practice, and solutions are urgently needed.

The methodological approach known as “living evidence” (LE) has emerged as a tool with the potential to address this need. It has been applied mainly to SRs, but currently it is not uncommon to find other types of evidence synthesis such as overviews or network meta-analysis presented as “living”.

A “living systematic review” is a SR that is continually updated, incorporating new relevant evidence as it becomes available. In practice, this means a continual surveillance for new research evidence through ongoing or frequent searches, and the inclusion of new information into the review in a timely manner so that the findings and conclusions of the SR remain current⁷. When the LE approach is applied to the resolution of relevant and rapidly changing clinical questions,

it ensures a rapid update of evidence synthesis that informs on the effects of controversial health interventions, and/or where there are uncertainties⁸.

The potential for LE to reduce the time and cost of updating evidence-based products and making it available to inform practice is enormous; nevertheless, it is necessary to weigh the potential benefits with the overload of time and resources that living synthesis entails.

The foundations of the LE model for SRs were initially stated in 2014⁷ and have been under development over the past few years⁹⁻¹¹. These have been used as the basis for the development and application of new strategies to keep the evidence supporting different products up to date. It has been of particular interest for the synthesis and dissemination of the exponential research output publishing during the COVID-19 pandemic¹². However, little guidance exists about the methods to be followed, and their validity and efficiency in achieving the appropriate integration of the studies that emerge every day in the already existing synthesis of evidence. There is also no clear route regarding the editorial processes that the periodic updates of the LE synthesis must follow.

With this SR we seek to identify and summarise the methods and procedures that different groups are currently using to generate and keep the evidence “living” and, to identify those aspects that permits assess the reliability and maintenance of the methodological quality of the synthesis through its multiple updates. We also aim to identify the different actions that current authors of living evidence synthesis are being carried out to alert readers of the evidence changes or periodic updates of the evidence synthesis, particularly of those that may have implications on clinical decisions, including the editorial processes, the informal alerts through evidence-based repositories, among others.

This systematic review is conducted as part of a larger knowledge transfer and a capacity- building project entitled “Living Evidence to Inform Health Decisions”¹³, funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation Marie Skłodowska-Curie programme (grant agreement No 894990). Results of this systematic review will contribute to the development of a LE implementation framework for health system organizations to use and incorporate the LE synthesis in the development of knowledge transfer products.

Protocol

This review complies with the ‘Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses’ (PRISMA) guidelines¹⁴ and will be carried out following recommendations outlined in The Cochrane Handbook of Systematic Review of Interventions¹⁵.

Search strategies

Electronic searches. Our main search source will be the [Epistemonikos](#) database, a comprehensive database of systematic reviews and other types of evidence, maintained by screening multiple information sources to identify SRs and their included

primary studies, including the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, Pubmed/MEDLINE, EMBASE, CINAHL, PsycINFO, LILACS, DARE, HTA Database, Campbell database, JBI Database of Systematic Reviews and Implementation Reports, EPPI-Centre Evidence Library¹⁶. An additional search using a highly sensitive search strategy will be performed on PubMed/MEDLINE, in order to compare results and be able to identify additional evidence synthesis reports not obtained from searches in Epistemonikos.

The searches will cover from the inception date of each database. No publication status or language restriction will be applied to the searches in Epistemonikos or to the additional searches.

The boolean search strategy that will be used and adjusted to each database is presented in [Table 1](#).

We will update the searches in Epistemonikos prior to the publication of this review, looking for updates to the already identified living evidence synthesis.

Additional searches. In order to identify articles that might have been missed in the electronic searches, we will email the contact authors of all the included studies to ask for additional publications of their SRs updates, particularly when there is no update published within a year from the last publication.

Eligibility criteria

Types of studies. We will include all types of LE synthesis reports. Any of the study types corresponding to the terms “Systematic review”; “meta-analysis”; “rapid review”; “review”; “network”; “network meta-analysis”; “scoping review”, “overview” and “evidence synthesis” will be included if it is linked to any of the following words or descriptions regarding the use of living strategy: “continuous updating”, “continuously updated”, “constantly updated”, “continual updating”, “continually updated”, “regular updating”, “regularly updated”, “updated regularly”, “regular updates”, “frequent updating”, “frequently updated”, “periodically updated”, “updated periodically”, “updated annually”, “annually updated”, “living”.

Each systematic review/overview and other study types previously mentioned, and subsequent publications of the same

review, arising because of the continuous “living” update process, will be included as a single study. However, each one of the subsequent publications of the same study will be reviewed in search of changes in the applied methodology, as well as to obtain information on the editorial implications

The selected articles must describe the methods used to keep the SR constantly updated. The method may either be completely new or may offer a better version of an existing method. The method does not need to have been well tested or used in a way that proves its value.

As a methodological review, our “intervention of interest” is the use of living evidence synthesis as part of the methods of a review assessing the evidence used for answering a clinical question, and therefore, we will exclude methodological or guidance papers.

Types of participants, interventions, and outcomes. Because our aim is to review the methodological approach used by authors to produce and maintain living evidence synthesis, we will include the studies (see “type of studies to be included”) addressing any type of condition and regardless of the participants or populations they have studied, the interventions or the exposures they have assessed, and the alternatives against which the intervention/exposure are being compared.

Selection of studies

We will use the [L.OVE](#) platform¹⁷ to manage the results from the search on Epistemonikos, and [Covidence](#)¹⁸ to manage the results from the search on MEDLINE (via Pubmed). In both, the duplicate references will be identified and eliminated by an automated process. A special algorithm comparing unique identifiers (database ID, DOI), and citation details (i.e., author names, journal, year of publication, volume, number, pages, article title and article abstract) will be implemented to ensure updates of the same study will not be identified as duplicates of the original publication. We will compare the final results of both processes as a validation of the sensitivity of the search strategy to identify “living evidence synthesis” as well as the sources of consultation (i.e. MEDLINE and Epistemonikos). The results will then be merged into a single list of potentially eligible studies.

Table 1. Search strategy.

1	(continuous updat*[tiab] OR continually updat*[tiab] OR constant updat*[tiab]) AND (systematic[sb] OR review[tiab] OR meta analys*[tiab] OR evidence[tiab] OR synthes*[tiab])
2	((living systematic review*[tiab]) OR (living meta analys*[tiab]) OR (living rapid review*[tiab]) OR (living rapid evidence[tiab]) OR (living review[tiab]) OR (living network[tiab]) OR (living evidence[tiab]) OR ((continuous updat*[tiab] OR continually updat*[tiab] OR constant updat*[tiab]))
3	((systematic[sb] OR review[tiab] OR meta analys*[tiab] OR evidence[tiab] OR synthes*[tiab])OR (synthes* OR review* OR network* OR evidenc* OR “systematic-review” OR “meta-analysis” OR “meta-analysis” OR “meta-analyses” OR metaanalys* OR “rapid-review” OR “rapid-evidence” OR overview* OR scoping*))

Two researchers (AA and JB) will independently screen the search results based on the title and abstract and confirm eligibility based on the inclusion criteria. We will retrieve the full-text article of the references that seems to meet the eligibility criteria or that require further analysis, to decide on their inclusion. Disagreements will be solved by reaching a consensus between reviewers. Each of the included articles and subsequent publications of the same review, arising as a result of the continuous “living” update process, will be linked and included as a single study. As part of the process of linking all publications of the same study, we will identify the original publication, the subsequent publications, and search manually for unpublished updates. In the case that the original publication was not identified as part of our search (e.g., was not originally published as living or to be continuously updated), we will run a special search to identify whether it is using related references, authors names, or title words; if necessary, we will perform a manual search.

We will report the results of this process in the PRISMA flowchart, where we will specify the reasons for any exclusion of the studies obtained in full text. We will include a modification of the PRISMA flowchart to be able to show not only the included articles but also their subsequent updating publications.

Data extraction

Two reviewers will independently extract data from each included article using a standardized form. We will extract data of the applied methodology for each of the articles relating to the same study (i.e. from all identified publications relating to the same study). We will search for changes in the initially proposed methodology or changes in methodological quality through the updates. The variables to be extracted have been defined by the present review’s authors, based on previous knowledge and developments for LE synthesis identified as part of the methodological literature review^{9–12,19,20} (see Table 2). Additional data will be extracted to allow the evaluation of the methodological aspects throughout the set of publications of the same study (e.g. the first publication of the synthesis and its subsequent updates) [see Table 3]. Extracted data will be presented in tables with key explanatory information.

Assessment of the methodological quality

We will assess the methodological quality of all included studies (e.g. SRs, overviews, or network meta-analysis) using the AMSTAR II checklist²¹ and other appropriate instruments according to the type of study (e.g. the NCCMT Quality Assessment Tool-Review articles²²). The assessment will be carried out on the original publication and all its

Table 2. Data to be extracted from each study.

Variable	Description/operational definition
Study ID	[Author Year] Study identification for each study
Title	Title of the article
Publication year	Year of the current article
DOI	DOI of this article
Publication	[1:Original/2:Update] To write 1 if this article is the first publication of the study; To write 2 if this article is an update
Identified through eligibility criteria	[Yes/No] To write Yes if this publication was identified through eligibility criteria; To write No if this publication was identified through additional manual search
Study design	[SR/LSR/Living Overview/LNMA] Study design of the article
Research group	[Cochrane/ other research group [define]/not reported] Research group involved in the article
Journal/Editorial Group/Publisher	Journal where the article has been published
Definition living methodology	[author of the reference/other(define)/NR] Definition used to describe living methodology if any
No. of authors maintaining the living process	[no. authors/NR] Number of authors involved in the living evidence synthesis
No. of databases used	Number and name of databases used during the search
Grey literature search	[Yes/No] To write Yes if they specify a grey literature search; to write No if do not specify a grey literature search
Who has performed the searches	[authors/specialized technician/external[contracted]/not reported] Person responsible to run the search

Variable	Description/operational definition
Technological enablers supporting searches	[yes/no/NR] Specify with yes or no if they used any technological enable to support the search
If yes, describe	Describe what technological enablers used to support the search
Search frequency	The frequency with which evidence searches are carried out (surveillance process)
Frequency of the updates	Frequency with which updates are planned (i.e. incorporate new data to the evidence synthesis)
Technological enablers supporting surveillance	[yes/no/NR] Specify if they use technological enablers that support the continue surveillance of the literature
If yes, describe	Describe which technological enablers that support the continue surveillance of the literature used
Funding	[define/none] Description of funding used to do the living evidence synthesis

Table 3. Variables to be extracted across publications of same study/review.

Variable	Description
Study ID	Study identification (number) for the group of publications
Number of updates	Number of updates from the first publication
Number of updated publications	Number of articles published from the first publication
Information publication agreement available?	[Yes/no] To write Yes if there is information about an information publication agreement available; To write No if there is no information about an information publication agreement available
Is there any change on the databases used during updates?	[yes/no] To write Yes if there is any change on the databases used during updates; to write No if there is no changes on the databases used during updates
If yes, which changes?	[define/NA] Describe which changes if any
Is there any change on the search strategy used during updates?	[yes/no] To write Yes if there is any change on the search strategy used during updates; to write No if there is no changes on the search strategy used during updates
If yes, which changes?	[define/NA] Describe which changes if any
Is there any other type of change on the methodology section during updates?	[Yes/No] To write Yes if there is any other change on the methodology section used during updates; to write No if there is not any other change on the methodology section used during updates
If yes, which changes	[define/NA] To define any other change found in the methodology section from the first publication to the last update.
PRISMA updated?	[Yes/No] To write Yes if the PRISMA flowchart has been updated after each searching/screening process; to write No if the PRISMA flowchart has not been updated
Integration of new evidence	[new republication/web-based/NR] Specify if the new evidence has been integrated through a new republication, an update web-based platform or not reported
Communicating review status	[web-based/other (define)/NR] To describe how is communicated to the readers that a new update is available
Editorial and peer review	[1: process is completed/2: not done/3: only alert/4: NR] To describe how the editorial and peer review is done for the original and for the updates.

subsequent updated publications. Two independent authors will complete the assessment of each included study (original and its linked publications); a third author will discuss the

final assessment with both authors who performed the initial evaluation and solve disagreements. We will present the results of this assessment in descriptive tables. We will pay par-

particular attention to changes in the methodological quality through publications of the same study.

Strategy for data synthesis

To present the data's basic features in the study, we will do a descriptive analysis (using frequencies, numbers, and proportions). We will present the results in tables, both for each selected article and for the group of publications linked to the same study. Qualitative data (e.g., description of the living methodology) will be presented in tables.

We will report the results in subgroups according to the type of study (LSR, Living overview, or LNMA).

PROSPERO registration

This protocol is registered under the accession number CRD42021248963.

Ethical considerations

As researchers will not access information that could lead to the identification of an individual participant, obtaining ethical approval was waived.

Data sharing

All data related to the project will be available. Epistemonikos Foundation will grant access to data.

Conclusions

The current way authors are incorporating LE in the systematic reviews or other type of evidence synthesis is unknown.

We are going to conduct a systematic review of studies reporting LE synthesis as part of the methods to solve health questions including systematic reviews, network meta-analysis and living overviews.

The aim of this review is to identify and summarise the methods and procedures that different groups are currently using to generate and keep the evidence “living” and, to identify those aspects that permits assess the reliability and maintenance of the methodological quality of the synthesis through its multiple updates.

Data availability

Underlying data

No data are associated with this article.

Reporting guidelines

Open Science Framework: PRISMA-P checklist for “Methods for living evidence synthesis: a systematic review protocol”. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/2QA4U>²³

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Zero “No rights reserved” data waiver](#) (CC0 1.0 Public domain dedication).

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Open Peer Review

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? **Nancy Santesso**

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Methods for living reviews are evolving and a study to determine the current methods being used by review authors will be important as we move forward, in particular if compared to the variety of methods being proposed today. Below I have included a few suggestions that may improve the paper.

I believe that this study is not a methodological review. My understanding of a methodological review is a review of studies that assess the effects of a method used in research (sometimes compared to another method), or association of a method with some outcome, and these effects or associations are pooled together across studies if possible (see Cochrane methodological reviews). To me, instead, this paper is a survey of what methods are currently being used. This may explain why on Page 4, the reference to the 'intervention of interest' does not seem to apply.

If you change this to a survey, the PRISMA checklist/statement would not be used when reporting this paper.

Since this study is about the methods for living reviews, I think it should be more broad. The information that will be extracted seems to focus mostly on the search methods, but there are other methods that are or could be affected when conducting a living review. I have mentioned a few below but I think the authors should explore the different methods that are currently being discussed in the literature and expand the data they will collect.

For example, the authors could consider adding how the results of the search and screening are reported as there seems to be some research about different methods of reporting being used. Alternatively, the authors may decide not to gather this data and instead refer to the paper by Kahale 2021.

There is also some literature about the statistical methods that could be used in living reviews (see

Simmonds 2017). The Simmonds paper identifies many important methods that could be used. The authors have not indicated that they will collect data about different methods of statistical analyses and interpretation, but could. In addition, there is some question about the criteria to decide when re-analysis and a subsequent publication should occur when doing a living review (e.g., it could be when results or certainty of evidence change, or simply when there is new evidence regardless of whether the effect or certainty changes). Data about if and how the authors of the reviews report these methodological decisions would likely be important to collect.

It's not clear to me why the methodological quality of the reviews are being assessed. How will this information be used? In addition, do the current tools actually address issues relevant to living reviews? Will these tools provide quality information relevant to a living review in particular?

A minor comment: I understand that different types of reviews will be included, but the paper may be easier to follow if the living 'reviews' are not referred to as 'studies'.

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[Publisher Full Text](#)

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Is the rationale for, and objectives of, the study clearly described?

No

Is the study design appropriate for the research question?

No

Are sufficient details of the methods provided to allow replication by others?

No

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Not applicable

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Systematic reviews and guideline development

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 22 Feb 2022

Maria Ximena Rojas Reyes, INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'HOSPITAL DE LA SANTA CREU I SANT PAU FUNDACION - IR-HSCSP, Spain

Dr. Santesso, we thank your careful reading of the manuscript and your constructive comments. We have taken them into account in order to improve and clarify the manuscript. Please find below a detailed point-by-point response to your comments. (Reviewer comments in italics)

Comment 1 *Methodological review vs methodological survey I believe that this study is not a methodological review. My understanding of a methodological review is a review of studies that assess the effects of a method used in research (sometimes compared to another method), or association of a method with some outcome, and these effects or associations are pooled together across studies if possible (see Cochrane methodological reviews). To me, instead, this paper is a survey of what methods are currently being used. This may explain why on Page 4, the reference to the 'intervention of interest' does not seem to apply. If you change this to a survey, the PRISMA checklist/statement would not be used when reporting this paper.*

Reply to comment 1 We have reviewed and is no clear nomenclature in biomedical literature for this type of study aimed to assess the methods used by others. Due to the lack of standardization between the terms "methodological survey", "methodological review" or "meta-epidemiological study", we decided to use "methodological study" rather than a "methodological review" to be informative and allow for appropriate indexing. A methodological study is defined as any study that describes or analyzes methods (design, conduct, analysis, or reporting) in published (or unpublished) literature. (Mbuagbaw *et al.*) We have introduced changes in our protocol according to this type of study design, which includes changes in the title and the methods section of this manuscript (see lines 136-147). Ref: Mbuagbaw, Lawrence & Lawson, Daeria & Puljak, Livia & Allison, David & Thabane, Lehana. (2020). A tutorial on methodological studies: The what, when, how and why. BMC Medical Research Methodology. 20. 226. 10.1186/s12874-020-01107-7.

Comment 2 *Exploring different methods of conducting a living review. Since this study is about the methods for living reviews, I think it should be broader. The information that will be extracted seems to focus mostly on the search methods, but there are other methods that are or could be affected when conducting a living review. I have mentioned a few below but I think the authors should explore the different methods that are currently being discussed in the literature and expand the data they will collect. For example, the authors could consider adding how the results of the search and screening are reported as there seems to be some research about different methods of reporting being used. Alternatively, the authors may decide not to gather this data and instead refer to the paper by Kahale 2021.*

Reply to comment 2 Prior to defining the variables to be collected, we conducted a review

of methodological and guidance articles published up to June 2021, all the references you have mentioned but Kahale 2021, were included and reviewed, they were already listed previously as part of the protocol references (see references 7 to 14 and 16, 21). The publication by Kahale 2021 was published later of our initial review but is now included as part of references reviewed: Ref N°13. Kahale L, Elkhoury R, El Mikati I, et al.: Tailored PRISMA 2020 flow diagrams for living systematic reviews: a methodological survey and a proposal. F1000Research. 2021; 10. Based on the previous work done by other authors, we defined the variables to be collected and exceed those related only to the search methods. This list already includes information about how results of the search and screening are reported, as we presented in tables 2 and 3. Nevertheless, taking into account your comments we have reviewed the list of variables and provided a better explanation of its operational definition (see tables 2 and 3).

Comment 3 *Data related statistical methods that could be used in living reviews*

There is also some literature about the statistical methods that could be used in living reviews (see Simmonds 2017). The Simmonds paper identifies many important methods that could be used. The authors have not indicated that they will collect data about different methods of statistical analyses and interpretation, but could. In addition, there is some question about the criteria to decide when re-analysis and a subsequent publication should occur when doing a living review (e.g., it could be when results or certainty of evidence change, or simply when there is new evidence regardless of whether the effect or certainty changes). Data about if and how the authors of the reviews report these methodological decisions would likely be important to collect.

Reply to comment 3 Even though the publication by Simmonds 2017 was included in our review of prior work done, we agree that still some variables related to statistical methods are needed. We have added new variables to collect specific information related to the statistical methods inspired in Simmonds 2017 work. See: "Data to be collected from the baseline report" in table 2- **Planning for evidence monitoring /surveillance**, and "Data to be collected from the updates" in table 2- **Information about the integration of new evidence (NEI)**

Comment 4 *The methodological quality of the reviews are being assessed*

It's not clear to me why the methodological qualities of the reviews are being assessed. How will this information be used? In addition, do the current tools actually address issues relevant to living reviews? Will these tools provide quality information relevant to a living review in particular?

Reply to comment 4 A living systematic review should derive from a reliable systematic review, the "baseline review". Our aim in conducting the methodological quality assessment of both, the baseline report and their subsequent updates, is to assess if the methodological quality is maintained, improved, or decreased through its multiple updates. We agree with you, the AMSTAR II checklist, as well as the other instruments we have proposed to use, are not addressing the relevant issues of living evidence synthesis or reviews. Even though we will use them for this assessment because they do address important quality issues that any systematic evidence synthesis should meet. We have improved the explanation of this procedure in the text: Lines 217-225. To be able of identifying the methodological quality of the baseline reviews and any variations through its

multiple updates, as part of the data collection we will assess the methodological quality of all included evidence synthesis reports using the appropriate instruments (i.e. AMSTAR II [checklist](#) for systematic reviews [21] and NCCMT Quality Assessment Tool-for other review articles [22]). Two independent authors will complete the assessment on the original publication (baseline review) and subsequent updated reports or publications. Disagreements will solve by consensus. We will pay particular attention to changes in the methodological quality through publications of the same review. Results of this assessment will be presented as part of the descriptive data in tables.

Comment 5. Reviews' nomenclature *A minor comment: I understand that different types of reviews will be included, but the paper may be easier to follow if the living 'reviews' are not referred to as 'studies'.*

Reply to comment 5 We have changed the references from “study/ies” to “review/s” throughout the manuscript. The change was introduced early in the text as follows: Line 154 Each report previously mentioned and the subsequent publications of the same review will be included and treated as a single study (i.e. review /evidence synthesis). After this, we use “review” for referring to the included evidence synthesis or reviews.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 06 October 2021

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.15135.r27710>

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Juan Erviti

Unit of Innovation and Organization, Navarre Health Service, Pamplona, Spain

This is a really interesting project that can provide relevant added value in the realm of systematic reviews. The protocol draft is sound and well written. Please find below some suggestions to the authors:

Search strategies

The draft reads as follows *“An additional search using a highly sensitive search strategy will be performed on PubMed/MEDLINE, in order to compare results and be able to identify additional evidence synthesis reports not obtained from searches in Epistemonikos”.*

This is intended to validate Epistemonikos as a database for searches on living reviews, including systematic reviews, network meta-analyses and living overviews. Since the main database for searching is Epistemonikos, it would be interesting to elaborate a little more about its quality and previous validation. Many readers may not be familiar to this database.

Assessment of the methodological quality

Authors will evaluate the quality of all included studies (e.g. SRs, overviews, or network meta-analysis) using the AMSTAR II checklist and other appropriate instruments according to the type of study (e.g. the NCCMT Quality Assessment Tool-Review articles).

Reference 21 in the draft is that of a previous version of the AMSTAR tool (published in 2007). Probably it would be better to swap the current reference 21 for the following:

Shea B J, Reeves B C, Wells G, Thuku M, Hamel C, Moran J et al. AMSTAR 2: a critical appraisal tool for systematic reviews that include randomised or non-randomised studies of healthcare interventions, or both *BMJ* 2017; 358 :j4008 doi:10.1136/bmj.j4008

An important limitation of the AMSTAR II tool is that the quality of individual studies in the meta-analysis is poorly evaluated. Domain 9 reads as follows: "*Did the review authors use a satisfactory technique for assessing the risk of bias (RoB) in individual studies that were included in the review?*"

There are two possible answers to this question, namely:

For *Partial Yes*, must have assessed RoB from

- unconcealed allocation, and
- lack of blinding of patients and assessors when assessing outcomes (unnecessary for objective outcomes such as all cause mortality)

For *Yes*, must also have assessed RoB from:

- allocation sequence that was not truly random, and
- selection of the reported result from among multiple measurements or analyses of a specified outcome

Likewise, the NCCMT Quality Assessment Tool-Review provides a poor approach to the RoB assessment of individual studies in the review (described on Question 6 of the tool).

Furthermore, in both AMSTAR II and NCCMT tools, the score in Domain 9 and Q6, respectively, is obtained simply if information on allocation, blinding, etc., has been *addressed*, regardless the resulting quality of individual studies included.

This is really poor approach to the RoB assessment of individual studies included in the reviews which is a key aspect for the reliability of published results. At present, the Cochrane collaboration is piloting its RoB2 tool. Ideally, RoB in the individual studies of the reviews should be re-assessed with the help of better tools like RoB2. If not possible, this should be stated in the protocol as a limitation of the LE systematic review.

Additional information on Table 2.

One of the variables included in Table 2 is the "Journal/Editorial Group/Publisher". I would also include the "impact factor" in order to showcase the "visibility" of living evidence. Likewise, the "Journal/Editorial Group/Publisher" and "impact factor" of the last update could also be included in Table 3.

References

1. Auladell-Rispau A, Bendersky J, Santafe A, Buchanan C, et al.: Methods for living evidence

synthesis: a systematic review protocol. *Open Research Europe*. 2021; **1**. [Publisher Full Text](#)
2. Shea B, Reeves B, Wells G, Thuku M, et al.: AMSTAR 2: a critical appraisal tool for systematic reviews that include randomised or non-randomised studies of healthcare interventions, or both. *BMJ*. 2017. [Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the rationale for, and objectives of, the study clearly described?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate for the research question?

Yes

Are sufficient details of the methods provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Not applicable

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: systematic reviews and pharmacoepidemiology

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 22 Feb 2022

Maria Ximena Rojas Reyes, INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'HOSPITAL DE LA SANTA CREU I SANT PAU FUNDACION - IR-HSCSP, Spain

Dr. Erviti, we thank your careful reading of the manuscript and your helpful comments and suggestions. Please find below our reply to your comments and suggestions. (Reviewer comments in italics)

Comment 1 *Search strategies The draft reads as follows "An additional search using a highly sensitive search strategy will be performed on PubMed/MEDLINE, in order to compare results and be able to identify additional evidence synthesis reports not obtained from searches in Epistemonikos".*

This is intended to validate Epistemonikos as a database for searches on living reviews, including systematic reviews, network meta-analyses, and living overviews. Since the main database for searching is Epistemonikos, it would be interesting to elaborate a little more about its quality and previous validation. Many readers may not be familiar with this database.

Reply to comment 1 We have decided not to carried out additional searches because Epistemonikos has been already validated for identification of any type of evidence syntheses. We have changed the paragraph and added a sentence with specific reference

(reference 17). Lines 161-168: With this aim we will use [Epistemonikos](#) database as the main source; this is a comprehensive database of systematic reviews and other types of evidence synthesis reports, maintained by screening multiple information sources to identify SRs and their included primary studies, including the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, Pubmed/MEDLINE, EMBASE, CINAHL, PsycINFO, LILACS, DARE, HTA Database, Campbell database, JBI Database of Systematic Reviews and Implementation Reports, EPPI-Centre Evidence Library [16]. This database has been validated, showing its completeness in collecting the published SRs and other type of evidence syntheses [17]*. *Reference 17: Rada, G., Pérez, D., Araya-Quintanilla, F. et al. Epistemonikos: a comprehensive database of systematic reviews for health decision-making. BMC Med Res Methodol 20, 286 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-020-01157-x>

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Reply to comment 2 We have updated the reference in the protocol according to your suggestion: Reference 22. Shea B J, Reeves B C, Wells G, Thuku M, Hamel C, Moran J et al. AMSTAR 2: a critical appraisal tool for systematic reviews that include randomised or non-randomised studies of healthcare interventions, or both BMJ 2017; 358 :j4008 doi:10.1136/bmj.j4008

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Likewise, the NCCMT Quality Assessment Tool-Review provides a poor approach to the RoB assessment of individual studies in the review (described on Question 6 of the tool).

Furthermore, in both AMSTAR II and NCCMT tools, the score in Domain 9 and Q6, respectively, is obtained simply if information on allocation, blinding, etc., has been addressed, regardless the resulting quality of individual studies included. This is really poor approach to the RoB assessment of individual studies included in the reviews which is a key aspect for the reliability of

published results. At present, the Cochrane collaboration is piloting its RoB2 tool. Ideally, RoB in the individual studies of the reviews should be re-assessed with the help of better tools like RoB2. If not possible, this should be stated in the protocol as a limitation of the LE systematic review.

Reply to comment 3 The goal of our analysis is to evaluate the methodological quality of the included SRs, from both the baseline one and their subsequent publications, but not the validity of the conclusions. We will then assess quality over time through the subsequent updates.

Comment 4. *Additional information on Table 2. One of the variables included in Table 2 is the "Journal/Editorial Group/Publisher". I would also include the "impact factor" in order to showcase the "visibility" of living evidence. Likewise, the "Journal/Editorial Group/Publisher" and "impact factor" of the last update could also be included in Table 3.*

Reply to comment 4 We have added the additional information regarding the "impact factor" on journal publication Living evidence products in table 2. We believe this variable will help to summarize the scope of the journal and add value to our descriptive analysis.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
